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8 **Black truffle cultivation: a global reality**

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15 **Abstract**

16 *Aim of study:* In recent decades the cultivation of the black truffle *Tuber melanosporum* has
17 expanded across all the Mediterranean-climate regions, but also to other regions outside the
18 European standard for the species. We aim to describe the current extent of *T. melanosporum*
19 cultivation.

20 *Area of study:* *Tuber melanosporum* plantations in Europe, the Mediterranean basin,
21 Australia, New Zealand, China, America and South Africa.

22 *Material and Methods:* The socioeconomic impact of *T. melanosporum* cultivation, the way in
23 which the current situation has been achieved and the knowledge needed for its progress are
24 reviewed.

25 *Research highlights:* *T. melanosporum* has been successfully cultivated in several countries
26 outside its natural area, but many practices are still empirical and thus yields cannot be
27 guaranteed. The recent advances in molecular techniques and genome science are helping to
28 overcome some of the difficulties traditionally constraining truffle research. The role of
29 truffles as a transitional element between agricultural and forestry activities makes its
30 cultivation a paradigm of sustainable rural development.

31 **Keywords:** *Tuber melanosporum*, Europe, Australia, New Zealand, Chile, USA.

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34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Wild edible fungi have traditionally been used as food or medicine worldwide (Boa, 2004).
37 Some of them – mostly saprotrophic – are cultivated (e.g. *Agaricus bisporus*), while many
38 others are exclusively harvested in forests. Truffles are one of the few cultivated mycorrhizal
39 fungi: they make part of the rural European culture, and nowadays they are widely used in
40 international haute cuisine.

41 The term “truffle” is sometimes used to generally name all hypogeous mushrooms, but it
42 specifically refers to the genus *Tuber*. Bonito *et al.* (2010) report at least 180 species of *Tuber*
43 around the world, although only about 13 have commercial interest (Bonito *et al.*, 2009). The
44 quintessential truffles are the European black truffle (*Tuber melanosporum* Vittad.) and the
45 Italian white truffle (*Tuber magnatum* Pico).

46 *T. melanosporum* was first cultivated in France during the 19th century (Olivier *et al.*, 1996)
47 and it is currently cultivated worldwide (mainly in regions with Mediterranean-like climate).
48 Despite research efforts cultivation is not completely domesticated. More recently, other
49 *Tuber* species have also been successfully cultivated, such as *Tuber aestivum* Vittad. and its
50 form *uncinatum*, *Tuber borchii* Vittad. and the *Tuber indicum* complex (Wang *et al.*, 2006)
51 (Chevalier and Frochot, 1997; Zambonelli *et al.*, 2000; Hu *et al.*, 2005), whereas the attempts
52 to grow the native North American *Tuber* species are in their first stages (Lefevre, 2012).
53 Much effort has been devoted to *T. magnatum*, although without success (Gregori, 2007;
54 Bencivenga *et al.*, 2009).

55 This review focuses on the current extent of *T. melanosporum* cultivation, which is by far the
56 most widespread. We describe its potential socioeconomic impact, the way in which the
57 current situation has been achieved and finally the knowledge needed for its progress.

58

59 **2. Socioeconomic and environmental values**

60 **2.1. Economic value**

61 In France, Italy, Spain and Australia truffles are currently a multi-million euro industry. In the
62 first three countries, truffles are harvested not only in planted truffle orchards (cultivated
63 truffles) but also in natural forests (wild truffles). The value of the *T. melanosporum*
64 production is estimated to be around 20 million euro per year in France (Escadre and Roussel,
65 2006), 7.5 million euro in Spain (estimated for the past decade on the basis of the mean prices
66 at Vic market, in north-eastern Spain), and 4 million euro in Australia in 2012 (Duell, 2012).
67 In Italy the value of the production of all species of *Tuber* together was estimated to be 18
68 million euro in 1999 (Pettenella *et al.*, 2004).

69 The price that farmers receive for *T. melanosporum* in Europe ranged in the past decade from
70 less than 150 to more than 800 euros kg⁻¹. The price for retail customers can be much higher:
71 e.g. in Paris and London prices higher than 2000-4000 euros kg⁻¹ can be achieved. This fact
72 has encouraged truffle growers to sell directly to restaurants and to use retail e-commerce. In
73 Australia the mean price in 2012 for the higher quality class was about 950 euros kg⁻¹ (Duell,
74 2012).

75 The high price of *T. melanosporum* makes its cultivation an interesting enterprise for farmers
76 wherever suitable environmental conditions exist. A review of economic evaluations of truffle
77 plantation in Europe by Bonet and Colinas (2001) showed that the internal rate of return (i.e.
78 the interest yield expected from the investment) was always above 9%, although the return
79 time of the investment was longer than 10 years. The GET (2002) estimated that markets
80 would be able to absorb around 1,000 t of *T. melanosporum*, which represents more than ten
81 times the current production. In Spain its current discounted value has increased at an annual
82 rate of 3% over the past 50 years (Reyna, 2007b).

83 The total economic impact includes not only fresh truffles sold by farmers, but also
84 agritourism, local mycological gastronomy, production of value-added truffle products, truffle
85 fairs and retail markets, increase in agricultural land price in truffle-growing regions,
86 production of mycorrhizal seedlings in nurseries, dog training, consumption of agricultural
87 supplies by truffle growers, technical assessment services, etc. The total economic impact of
88 *T. melanosporum* was estimated to be around 70 million euros per year in France (Escadre and
89 Roussel, 2006). In Italy, the total economic impact of all *Tuber* species together was
90 estimated to be more than 100 million euros (Gregori, 2013).

91

92 **2.2. Social value: rural development**

93 In many *T. melanosporum*-producing regions of the Mediterranean basin the environmental
94 conditions and the small size of plots limit the yield of traditional agricultural crops (Pinto-
95 Correia, 1993). Truffle cultivation represents an alternative for their agriculture: an economic
96 diversification and an extra income. When non-agricultural activities are brought into play
97 (e.g. agritourism) truffle fulfils a more robust role in rural development. Besides, maintaining
98 marginal agricultural lands cultivated helps to preserve the traditional Mediterranean
99 agroforestry landscapes and rural population.

100 The harvesting of wild *T. melanosporum* also plays a role in the rural economy of Italy and
101 Spain. The value that truffles add to forests is particularly interesting in Mediterranean

102 forests: given their low productivity (Domínguez-Torres and Plana, 2002) it could promote
103 involvement of the rural communities in forest protection and management.

104 In Italy and France truffles are a part of the rural cultural heritage and a reason for pride.
105 Truffle has encouraged the development of partnerships and associations of growers,
106 municipalities (such as the Italian *Città del Tartufo*) and gourmets. Ecomuseums such as those
107 in Sorges (France), San Giovanni d'Asso (Italy) and Metauten (Spain) introduce the public to
108 the various aspects of truffles.

109

110 **2.3. Environmental value**

111 In its natural area, *T. melanosporum* can be grown with low environmental impact: the use of
112 machinery and chemicals is limited, so it can be easily considered organic farming. Soil tilling
113 of these plots increases water infiltration rates. The maintenance of soil conservation
114 structures limits soil erosion risk in steep slopes. The use of native *Quercus* as host plants
115 contributes to the conservation of natural forests. In the fire-prone Mediterranean landscapes,
116 *T. melanosporum* plantations constitute excellent firebreaks due to low plantation densities,
117 soil tilling and the herbicidal effect of the fungus.

118

119 **3. The history of truffle cultivation**

120 Hypogeous fungi (most probably desert truffles of the genera *Terfezia* and *Tirmania*) were
121 consumed in the Antiquity by Mesopotamians, Egyptians, Greeks and Romans. During the
122 Middle Ages they are scarcely cited in Europe, but in the Renaissance truffles gained a
123 reputation in Italy and in France, and truffle consumption spread among wealthy people
124 (Reyna, 2007a). Manna (2005) reports harvest regulations in Italy during this period.
125 Ceccarelli wrote a monograph on the management of wild *truffières* in 1564 (Granetti, 2005).
126 During the 18th and 19th centuries the consumption of truffles increased thanks to gourmets
127 such as Brillat-Savarin. This encouraged the spreading of truffle harvesting and the
128 management of wild *truffières*. A major advance occurred in the early 19th century when the
129 French farmer Joseph Talon had the idea of sowing acorns from truffle-producing trees near
130 or inside the *truffières*. Auguste Rousseau disseminated the technique and thousands of
131 hectares of oaks were planted thanks to this idea, boosted by the French reforestation laws of
132 1860 and 1882 (Diette and Lauriac, 2005) and the expansion of available agricultural land due
133 to the widespread vineyard destruction by the *Phylloxera* plague (Olivier *et al.*, 1996). This
134 resulted in the golden age for truffle production, with estimated productions of 1,588 t in
135 1868, and 2,000 t in 1892. In Italy, Mattiolo and Francolini also promoted reforestations to

136 increase truffle production (Granetti, 2005). In those decades De Bosredon, Chatin and Pradel
137 wrote monographs on truffle ecology and cultivation. During the same period Carlo Vittadini
138 provided the first detailed morphological descriptions of many *Tuber* sporocarps and a
139 classification system (Trappe *et al.*, 2009).

140 In the 20th century French production sharply declined to the current 10-60 t per year, due to
141 the rural depopulation caused by the two World Wars and by the rural to urban drift. The
142 forest stand density increased and much of farmers' empirical knowledge was lost (Olivier *et*
143 *al.*, 1996). In Italy the decline was not so severe and limited to the first half of the century
144 (Manna, 1990). In the late 1960s the progress in truffle cultivation seemed arrested despite the
145 works of Rebière and Mannoizzi-Torini.

146 A breakthrough occurred in the early 1970s, when researchers from the IPLA and the INRA
147 developed the inoculation of seedlings with *Tuber* in the nursery (Chevalier, 2001). Almost
148 90 years before, Frank had coined the term mycorrhiza and postulated that this structure
149 involved a symbiotic relationship (Trappe *et al.*, 2009). *T. melanosporum*-inoculated
150 seedlings were released to the market in France in 1973 (Chevalier, 2001), greatly increasing
151 plantation activity. On the other hand, in Italy it gained momentum from 1982 (Bencivenga,
152 2001).

153 At that time French truffle growers had already begun to associate, and the government had
154 established public aids for plantation establishment (Olivier *et al.*, 1996). Italy organised the
155 first International Truffle Congress in 1968. Up to the 1980s the intensive cultivation
156 techniques (Pallier method) were dominant in plantations, whereas from the 1990s more
157 extensive models (Tanguy method) were proposed (Olivier *et al.*, 1996).

158 Spain only became involved in the international truffle market in the 1960s, when wild
159 *truffières* across the country began to be systematically searched and exploited. An alarming
160 decrease in production was observed from the 1980s, after 20-30 years of intensive harvesting
161 in a context of rural depopulation and increasing forest stand density. Except for the Arotz
162 estate (around 600 ha planted in the 1970s), the plantation of mycorrhizal seedlings was
163 minimal until the 1990s. In that decade truffle growers began to associate, and regional
164 governments established public assistance for the establishment of plantations.

165

166 **4. Current state in France, Italy and Spain**

167 The annual European production of *T. melanosporum* was an average of around 56 t for the
168 period 2001-2010, although highly variable from year to year (Table 1, Fig. 1).

169 In France, the production seems steady since the 1990s (Fig. 1), despite the rate of plantation
170 (Table 1). Our estimation of mean yield in mature plantations is very low (Table 1), but it is
171 consistent with the 0.5-3 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ cited by Escafre and Roussel (2006).

172 French growers benefit from a high domestic demand (it consumes most of the French and
173 Spanish production), the support from public agencies to plantation establishment (Sourzat,
174 2007), and an extensive network of scientists and specialists (although much of their work is
175 not published in scientific journals) (Table 1). The experience of experimental stations in
176 which researchers and growers closely collaborate, such as that of Le Montat (Lot), seems
177 especially interesting.

178 In Italy, we estimate that the mean yield of mature plantations is similar to that of France
179 (Table 1). The strengths of *T. melanosporum* cultivation are also similar, with a greater
180 emphasis on exportation (Galluzzo, 2013). The introduction of exotic species such as *T.*
181 *indicum* s.l. and *Tuber sinoaestivum* Zhang et Liu (Zhang *et al.*, 2012) in Italian orchards may
182 become a serious problem (Murat *et al.*, 2008; Zambonelli *et al.*, 2012).

183 In Spain, plantations have made up for the collapse of wild production over the past few
184 decades (Fig. 1). The mean yield of mature plantations is somewhat higher than in France and
185 Italy (Table 1), despite the fact that the mean age of plantations is lower (plantation
186 establishment started later). In the Arotz plantation the yield in the late 1990s was lower than
187 2 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ in non-irrigated areas, and up to 45 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ in the irrigated areas
188 (Carbajo, 1999).

189 Domestic consumption of truffles in Spain is less than 10%, and promotion activities such as
190 fairs are still limited (Table 1). In some regions the high plantation rates during the 2000s
191 were mainly due to grants covering 100% of the cost of plantation establishment (excluding
192 land purchase), thus making planting a business in itself. Some experts argue that a part of
193 these plantations will not be carefully managed and will be less likely to succeed.

194

195 **5. Cultivation outside the native range**

196 **5.1. North America**

197 The first *T. melanosporum*-inoculated plantations were established in 1979 in North Carolina
198 and 1980 in California, and the first sporocarps were harvested in 1987 in northern California
199 (Renowden, 2005; Lefevre, 2012). Nowadays there are plantations from California to
200 southern British Columbia (Canada) and from central Texas to North Carolina (Renowden,
201 2005; Lefevre, 2012). Most of them were planted after 2003 (Pilz *et al.*, 2009). Sporocarp
202 production has been reported in California, North Carolina, Tennessee, Texas, Oregon and

203 British Columbia (Lefevre, 2012; Berch, 2013). Soils are usually limed to raise the pH. *C.*
204 *avellana*, *Q. robur* and *Q. ilex* are commonly used as host plants.

205 These plantations have usually spread without any coordinated initiative or technical
206 assessment. Furthermore, in some cases the sites are far from the climatic requirements of *T.*
207 *melanosporum* (Lefevre, 2012). The overall yields are far from optimum (Table 2).

208

209 **5.2. Australia and New Zealand**

210 New Zealand was the first country in the Southern Hemisphere to establish *T. melanosporum*
211 plantations (in 1987) and to harvest sporocarps (in 1993). The initiative was led by a scientist
212 (Ian Hall), supported by the government (Hall and Haslam, 2012). Its development was based
213 on climatic and edaphic studies, production of mycorrhizal seedlings in the country and
214 quality control of mycorrhizal seedlings. A variety of field essays were established to
215 determine the best management practices (Guerin-Laguette *et al.*, 2009). However, most
216 information remains unpublished due to confidentiality (Hall and Haslam, 2012). *C. avellana*
217 and *Q. robur* were initially used as host plants, and *Q. ilex* was introduced later (Zambonelli
218 *et al.*, 2009).

219 Australia began to plant some years later and benefited from New Zealand experience,
220 important subsidies for plantation establishment and a more continued government support
221 for research (Hall and Haslam, 2012), thus being reflected in the planted surface (Table 2).
222 Plantations are currently common in Western Australia (notably around Manjimup and
223 Pemberton), Tasmania, New South Wales and Victoria (Lee, 2008). The agricultural practices
224 have been adapted to the environmental conditions: they are more intensive than in Europe
225 and plantation densities are higher (Zambonelli *et al.*, 2009).

226 The productive results in both countries are contrasting (Fig. 2): we estimate that the mean
227 yield of mature plantations is 0.5 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ for New Zealand and 9.2 kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ for
228 Australia. The latter can be considered an important success, although the differences in
229 productivity among plots are high and most production comes from a limited number of
230 plantations (Hall and Haslam, 2012).

231 One important advantage for these countries is that forests are dominated by endomycorrhizal
232 plants or ectomycorrhizal fungi very different from the European ones (Zambonelli *et al.*,
233 2009). As calcareous soils are scarce, liming the soil is a common practice, like in North
234 America, and rising of the pH can also reduce the competitiveness of the scarce
235 ectomycorrhizal fungi (Lefevre and Hall, 2000). Australia and New Zealand produce in
236 counter-season to the main producers and consumers, and this helps their exports given that

237 the truffles are mostly consumed fresh. In addition, their domestic demand is rapidly
238 increasing: truffle fairs are organised to spread its culinary use, and about 800 kg were
239 consumed in Australia in 2012 (Duell, 2012), with the bulk exported.

240 The success of some plantations is threatened by the accidental introduction of *T. brumale*
241 (through the imported sporocarps used as inoculum) in both countries (Linde and Selmes,
242 2012; Guerin-Laguette *et al.*, 2013).

243

244 **5.3. China**

245 The first *T. indicum* s.l. plantation was established in Taiwan in 1989, and the first sporocarps
246 were harvested in 1997 (Hu *et al.*, 2005). In continental China, the first *T. indicum* s.l.
247 sporocarps and the first *T. melanosporum* sporocarps were harvested in neighbouring
248 plantations in Guizhou (Wang, 2012). Another *T. melanosporum* plantation was established in
249 Hunan (Wang, 2012), despite the excessive summer temperatures and low winter
250 temperatures (Hall, 2013). More *T. indicum* s.l. plantations have been established in recent
251 years in Guizhou, Hunan, Sichuan and Yunnan using native *Quercus*, *Pinus* and *Castanea* as
252 hosts (Wang, 2012).

253 In most cases these activities were supported by universities and implied the development of
254 nursery techniques. However, quality control of seedlings is not common and many
255 plantations are established on forest soils (Wang, 2012). Most truffles are exported and the
256 domestic demand is low.

257

258 **5.4. Europe and the Mediterranean basin**

259 *T. melanosporum* cultivation is being essayed across Europe and the Mediterranean basin.
260 However, these plantations are still young and sparse, and in many cases the sites do not fulfil
261 *T. melanosporum* climatic requirements. Some plantations have already produced sporocarps
262 in Israel, Morocco and Sweden (Khabar 2007; Turgeman *et al.*, 2012; Wedén *et al.*, 2013).

263 The interest on *T. aestivum*/*T. uncinatum* cultivation is also recent and widespread. These
264 plantations are more likely to succeed given the wider ecological requirements of this species
265 (Stobbe *et al.*, 2013). Israel is an illustrating example (Turgeman *et al.*, 2012). In 1994 *T.*
266 *melanosporum*-inoculated seedlings were planted, and in 1999 a sporocarp was harvested. But
267 in 2002 it was impossible to find *T. melanosporum* mycorrhizas in the plantation. In 1999
268 more seedlings were planted, but *T. aestivum*-inoculated seedlings were non-intentionally
269 introduced. In 2010 about 15 kg ha⁻¹ of *T. aestivum* were harvested and it has continued to
270 fruit.

271

272 **5.5. South America and South Africa**

273 Following New Zealand's example, the Universidad Católica del Maule started a project to
274 cultivate *T. melanosporum* in Chile with government support (Fundación para la Innovación
275 Agraria). The first plantation was established in 2003 and the first truffles were harvested in
276 2009 (Table 2). Most plantations are located between the regions of Valparaíso and Los Ríos.
277 Soils are usually limed to raise pH. *Q. robur*, *Q. ilex* and *C. avellana* are the most used host
278 plants (Henríquez, pers. comm., www.trufaschile.cl).

279 The initiative was based on a climatic and edaphic study of Chile, and the development of
280 nursery techniques to produce mycorrhizal seedlings. More recently, the public initiative is
281 addressed to establish field essays aimed at determining the best management practices and
282 the environmental factors that enhance fruiting. Public efforts have been also launched to
283 promote the association of growers, to train farmers and to develop commercial strategies.
284 Being in the Southern Hemisphere, Chile has the opportunity to produce counter-season to
285 Europe. In contrast, their domestic demand is still very low, and their farmers need technical
286 assessment on quality of mycorrhizal seedlings and management practices.

287 In 2008 a nursery was established in Argentina and the first seedlings were planted in 2010
288 (Table 2). The first plantations are located in south Buenos Aires region and Río Negro
289 (Henríquez, pers. comm.). People in neighbouring countries like Uruguay, Peru and Brazil
290 have recently shown interest in starting truffle cultivation projects (Henríquez, pers. comm.).

291 In South Africa, *T. melanosporum* plantations were initiated in 2008 through a joint venture
292 and the establishment of several nurseries (Table 2). *Q. robur*, *C. avellana* and *Q. ilex* are the
293 most used host plants (Miros, pers. comm., <http://woodfordtruffles.co.za/>).

294

295 **6. Basic research**

296 The cultivation of *T. melanosporum* is not completely domesticated, as the uncertainties
297 around the mating process remain (Selosse *et al.*, 2013). Basic research on truffles has been
298 constricted by the difficulties to observe their development: the symbiotic phase is
299 microscopic and the growth of the mycelium in pure culture is slow, whereas the sporocarp
300 grows underground and over a period of several months.

301 In recent years molecular techniques are allowing for great progress: they are used to identify
302 sporocarps, mycorrhizas and mycelia; to recognise genetically identical individuals (genets);
303 and to determine the molecular bases of truffle biology. The genome of *T. melanosporum* has
304 been recently sequenced by the *Tuber* Genome Consortium, opening the possibilities of

305 genomics to truffle research (Martin *et al.*, 2010). These tools support novel approaches to
306 important research gaps in the mechanisms regulating symbiosis, the trophic state of the
307 fungus, population genetics and the mechanisms involved in fruiting. Linking gene functions
308 and interactions with the biology and ecology of the fungus will improve the design and
309 management of plantations.

310 An important breakthrough has been the confirmation that *T. melanosporum* is heterothallic
311 (Riccioni *et al.*, 2008), the identification of two mating types, and the characterisation of the
312 genes involved (Rubini *et al.*, 2011a). However, the sex organs are still largely unknown: only
313 ascogonia have been rarely reported (Callot, 1999). Le Tacon *et al.* (2013) hypothesised that
314 the ascogonium connects the mycorrhiza to the sporocarp during all its development.

315 The understanding of the ectomycorrhizal relation is being improved by recent studies on the
316 signalling pathways to its establishment, the mechanisms of the fungus to inhibit the
317 defensive response of the plant, the mechanisms of the partners to control each other, the role
318 of nutrients transfer in the maintenance of the relation, the ability of the fungus to cleave
319 sucrose (Plett and Martin, 2011) or the role of truffle volatiles in the first contact (Splivallo *et*
320 *al.*, 2011).

321 Although *T. melanosporum* retains some genes encoding enzymes responsible for degrading
322 plant living cells, it has less degradative enzymes than saprotrophic fungi, thus indicating a
323 lower ability to degrade organic tissues (Plett and Martin, 2011). This makes the fungus
324 highly dependent on its host: Le Tacon *et al.* (2013) found that even in the late stages of the
325 sporocarp development most carbon was supplied by the plant. The analysis of the
326 transcription factors can help to understand the variations in the trophic behaviour of the
327 fungus in each developmental stage (Montanini *et al.*, 2011).

328 The methods for quantifying mycelium of *T. melanosporum* in the soil have allowed Liu *et al.*
329 (2014) to monitor its spread and increase of density in young plantations. Suz *et al.* (2008)
330 showed the relation between the abundance of mycelium and the formation of the *brûlé*. Liu
331 *et al.* (2014) also hypothesised the existence of a mycelium-carrying capacity of the soil, and
332 it would be interesting to understand the relation of this with the abundance of volatiles.

333 Murat *et al.* (2013) found that *T. melanosporum* genets in young plantations were mostly
334 small (diameter lower than 1 m), and few of them were found from year to year. Rubini *et al.*
335 (2011b) showed that in the nursery genets compete each other for root tips, leading to the
336 exclusion of most genets in 18 month-old seedlings. In the field intraspecific competition
337 causes a spatial separation between mating types that can affect fruiting potential (Rubini *et*
338 *al.*, 2011b). Selosse *et al.* (2013) hypothesised that the mating-type genes could also be

339 controlling vegetative incompatibility, but Iotti *et al.* (2012) did not find genes related to
340 mating-type heterokaryon incompatibility in *T. melanosporum*.

341 The understanding of the mechanisms triggering fruiting is being improved by the studies on
342 the regulome involved in developmental shifts from the symbiotic to the reproductive phase,
343 on carbon transfer from the plant to the sporocarp, and on mating types. But it is also essential
344 to know which factors of the soil environment are involved: Pacioni *et al.* (2014) suggested
345 that variations in soil temperature and water content in spring are key, and proposed to use
346 ground penetrating radars to monitor the sporocarps without disturbing their environment.

347 The translation of basic research to agricultural practices can be obscured by the interaction
348 between *T. melanosporum* and other soil organisms (e.g. fungal competitors, bacteria
349 modulating the mycorrhizal relation, or interacting with the fruiting). Metagenomics makes
350 the study of soil microbial communities easier.

351

352 **7. Cultivation challenges**

353 Nowadays many of the practices in *T. melanosporum* cultivation are still empirical. The
354 success of plantations cannot be guaranteed: plantations largely differ in the sporocarp yield,
355 the percentage of productive trees and the age at which they start producing (productive
356 onsets at age 4 and later than year 15 have been reported).

357 The quality of some nursery seedlings is a problem in countries without mandatory
358 certification systems. It can be the cause of failure for some plantations and the way that
359 exotic species are introduced. The production of seedlings with known mating types is a
360 challenge for the future, since they are currently inoculated with spores (Rubini *et al.*, 2011b).

361 The experience in North America and the Southern Hemisphere proved that it is possible to
362 grow truffles in naturally acidic soils after liming. But if not enough lime is added to stabilise
363 the pH, it decreases in a few years, making periodic liming necessary.

364 Sourzat (2008, 2010) drew attention to other soil-related issues jeopardising the success of
365 plantations in France: the chemicals applied in the previous land use and the high pressure of
366 ectomycorrhizal competitors (particularly *T. brumale* and *T. aestivum*) in landscapes
367 dominated by forest patches. The competition of soil-borne fungi points to the need to
368 understand better the factors determining the structure of ectomycorrhizal communities and
369 their dynamics, including the possible role of truffle volatiles (Splivallo *et al.*, 2011).

370 In contrast, in Spain the plantations are usually located in extensive agricultural landscapes,
371 so these problems are less frequent. However, the temperatures are higher and the rainfall is

372 more scarce and irregular. This reduces the survival of the sporocarps during the summer,
373 making research on irrigation and soil water conservation a priority.

374 Other challenges in French plantations (Sourzat, 2008, 2010) are the short productive life of
375 some young plantations and the high stand densities in mature plantations. The latter draws
376 attention to the importance of pruning and thinning. Old plantations (planted before the
377 1970s) which are not producing currently are seen as an opportunity for spreading truffle
378 production by forest management.

379 Large concentrations of plantations pose new threats: e.g. the truffle growers in Sarrión
380 (Teruel) complain that in recent years the damages of insects on sporocarps are increasing,
381 especially in dry and hot autumns.

382 Outside France and Italy most plantations are still young and management techniques are not
383 adapted to the local conditions (soil water and temperature regimes, aeration, organic matter,
384 host plants, soil-borne ectomycorrhizal community, etc.) yet. There is not a unique
385 management system that works in all the environmental conditions suitable for *T.*
386 *melanosporum* growth. Monitoring mycorrhizas and mycelium, tree growth and physiology,
387 and soil microclimate in these plantations is highly recommendable. This way it could be
388 assured that they remain potentially successful, and the management practices could be
389 quickly improved.

390 A major problem in Australia is the abundance of sporocarps growing near the soil surface in
391 irrigated plantations. These are more frequently damaged by pests, diseases, desiccation and
392 frosts. The first studies on the matter point that reducing the irrigation and increasing the
393 irrigation interval could help to decrease the damages (Eslick and Dell, 2013).

394 In countries with a meaningful wild production (Spain and Italy) the conservation of this
395 production is an important concern: this involves sustainable harvesting and habitat
396 improvement (Garcia-Barreda and Reyna, 2013).

397 Finally, if the climate change predictions for the Mediterranean basin (decrease in summer
398 rainfall, increase of temperatures and increase in interannual variability of both rainfall and
399 temperature) are confirmed, the suitability of many native *T. melanosporum* areas for
400 cultivation (specially the warmest ones) will be reduced (Colinas *et al.*, 2007). A planning
401 effort will be needed to assess the future suitability of the current native range and to adapt
402 the cultural practices to the new situation.

403

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407

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Table 1. Main features of *T. melanosporum* production and associate activities in France, Italy and Spain

	France	Italy	Spain
Mean production between seasons 2003-2004 and 2012-2013 (t year ⁻¹) ¹	31.3	11.0	15.9
% truffles produced in plantations vs harvested in the wild ²	90%-10%	50%-50%	60%-40%
Plantation surface (ha) ³	24,000	7,500	10,000
Recent rate of plantation (ha year ⁻¹) ³	800	400	1000
Mean yield of mature plantations (kg ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹) ⁴	1.5	1.2	3.2
Main productive regions ²	Drôme (>6,500 ha), Lot, Vaucluse, Dordogne, Gard	Marche (aprox. 5,000 ha), Umbria, Abruzzo	Teruel (>4,000 ha), Soria, Huesca, Castelló
Hosts in plantations ⁵	Qh, Qi, Qr, Ca	Qh, Qi, Oc, Ca	Qi, Ca, Qf, Qc
No of nurseries ⁶	27	8	27
Price of seedlings (euros) ⁶	5-19	8-14	4-8
No of growers/harvesters ⁷	20,000	180,000 ⁷	10,000
No of growers/harvesters associations ⁷	36	50	20
No of truffle fairs and retail markets ⁸	129	68 in Umbria, Piemont, Toscana and Abruzzo	15
No of research articles (and No of citations) on truffles (2008-2012) ⁹	13 (179)	43 (209)	32 (118)

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¹ According to the European Group for Truffles, Oliach (pers. comm.) and Gregori (pers. comm.).

² According to Gregori (2007) and Sourzat (2007).

³ Estimated from Escafre and Roussel (2006) and Gregori (2007).

⁴ We estimated the mean yield of mature plantations (1) taking into account the proportion of wild production, (2) assuming that young plantations (less than seven years old) do not have a quantitatively meaningful production, and (3) estimating the surface of young plantations from the recent plantation rate.

⁵ Qh: *Quercus humilis* Mill. (= *Q. pubescens*), Qi: *Quercus ilex* L, Qr: *Quercus robur* L, Ca: *Corylus avellana* L, Oc: *Ostrya carpinifolia* Scop., Qf: *Quercus faginea* Lam., Qc: *Quercus coccifera* L.

⁶ According to Cocina *et al.* (2013).

⁷ According to GET (2002). Pettenella *et al.* (2004) estimated that only 5% of the Italian harvesters are professionals.

⁸ Including events dedicated to any *Tuber* species. According to Cena (2000), Materozzi (2005), FFT (2011), Marone (2011) and FFT (2012).

⁹ According to Web of Science. Only articles in which the first author works in a research centre of the country are considered. Articles on all species of *Tuber* are considered.

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Table 2. Main features of *T. melanosporum* plantations outside its natural distribution area

	USA	New Zealand	Australia	Chile	South Africa	Argentina
Date of first plantation	1979	1987	1993	2003	2008	2010
Production (kg year ⁻¹) ¹	40	<50	4,500	7	0	0
Plantation surface (ha) ²	120	100	700	200	30	40
Recent rate of plantation (ha year ⁻¹) ³	20	Very low	30	35	10	20
No of nurseries ⁴	4	4	6	4	2	2
Price of seedlings (euros) ⁴	11-19	28-33	15-46	10-15	11	12

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¹ According to Lefevre (2010), Duell (2012), Guerin-Laguette *et al.* (2013) and Henríquez (pers. comm.)

² According to Pilz *et al.* (2009), Zambonelli *et al.* (2009), Hall and Haslam (2012), Henríquez (pers. comm.) and Miros (pers. comm.)

³ According to Treloar (2013); to the comparison of current surfaces to those 5-7 years ago (Ramírez *et al.* 2007; Lee 2008); and in the case of the USA to seedling production of the most important nurseries (Cocina *et al.* 2013) and common plantation densities.

⁴ According to Cocina *et al.* (2013).

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Figure 1. Estimates for *T. melanosporum* production from season 1990-1991 in France, Italy, Spain (according to the European Group for Truffles for the data up to 2009-2010, and to Oliach, pers. comm. and Gregori pers. comm. for the recent ones) and Australia (Duell, 2012).

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Figure 2. Estimation of current production of *T. melanosporum*.